

Optimal Charging Strategy Design for Lithium-ion Batteries Considering Minimization of Temperature Rise and Energy Loss

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Abstract: Battery charging techniques are critical to enhance battery operation performance. Charging temperature rise, energy loss and charging time are three key indicators to evaluate charging performance. It is imperative to decrease temperature rise and energy loss without extending the charging time during the charging process. To this end, an equivalent circuit electrical model, a power loss model and a thermal model are built in this study for lithium-ion batteries. Then, an integrated objective function is formulated to minimize energy loss and temperature increment during battery charging. To further validate the generality and feasibility of the proposed charging strategy, experiments are conducted with respect to different current, operating temperatures, battery types and aging status. Comparison results demonstrate that the devised charging strategy is capable of achieving the intended effect under any operating temperature and with different aging status.

Key Words: Battery charging, closed-form expression, minimization, thermal model, Lagrange multiplier.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the development of electric vehicles (EVs) cannot be independent of advanced battery technologies [1-5], and lithium-ion batteries seem to be the most competitive candidate due to their reasonable power and energy density, long life cycle and memoryless effect [6, 7]. To ensure safe and healthy battery operation, and to extend battery life to the greatest extent, a variety of research has been

30 carried out to estimate internal battery status, e.g. state of charge (SOC) [8-10], state of energy (SOE) [11],
31 state of power (SOP) [12] and state of health (SOH) [13-15]. In addition, balancing techniques used for
32 cells [16], thermal management [17] and charging strategies [18, 19] are also critical to ensure battery
33 operation with high performance. In particular, the charge control is one of the most important factors and
34 can affect the charging speed, efficiency, temperature rise and even battery lifespan.

35 Currently, a variety of lithium-ion battery charging strategies have been proposed, such as the typical
36 constant current (CC), constant voltage (CV), pulse current (PC) and intelligent charging strategies [20, 21].
37 The CC strategy charges a battery with a constant current until the battery voltage attains a preset level.
38 Various algorithms have been proposed to improve its efficiency [22-27], but most of them were tested
39 within a narrow temperature range, meaning the temperature effect was not fully taken into account. For
40 the CV charging strategy, the battery terminal voltage is kept unchanged at a preset value, and the charging
41 current gradually decreases to a cutoff value. The CV method can avoid overcharge and prevent irreversible
42 internal reactions of the battery, which may lead to undesired degradation of the battery lifetime [28]. In
43 practice, the combined CC-CV charging strategy is widely employed, in which the CV charging stage is
44 imposed after the battery terminal voltage increases to a predetermined maximum value under the CC mode
45 [26]. In this manner, the advantages of the CC and CV strategies can both be exploited. However, with the
46 increase of charging-depletion cycles, battery polarization becomes increasingly inevitable [29]. To
47 mitigate its influence, the PC mode is proposed, in which the charging current is intermittently applied with
48 a preset value and a predetermined frequency. During the charging process, there exists a certain interval
49 of rest or reverse discharging current between two pulses, by which the polarization effect can be eliminated
50 to some extent, and the charging speed can thus be improved [30]. That said, a faster charging speed may
51 result in the generation of enormous heat due to the internal resistance of the battery and thus lead to
52 temperature rise and possible capacity degradation acceleration [31]. Intelligent charging strategies are
53 favorable as they are capable of increasing charging speed while controlling the temperature rise. Under
54 such strategies, batteries are charged in a short period until the terminal voltage attains a preset threshold,
55 and then the charging current is adapted dynamically according to the variation of battery SOC and SOH

56 [10, 32, 33]. These kinds of strategies only aim at increasing charging speed [34] and do not consider the
57 charging energy loss.

58 Most importantly, the aforementioned charging strategies do not fully take heat generation into account
59 and rarely discuss its effect on battery parameters [35]. In terms of most existing strategies, the relationship
60 among internal resistance, polarization resistance, open circuit voltage (OCV) and SOC is solely considered
61 under a certain temperature, and these strategies are widely employed without considering the observed
62 thermal effect in practice [35]. In reality, a significant change in temperature is inevitable in EVs and the
63 corresponding change in battery parameter variation can and should be found [36]. The lithium ion in a
64 battery is active and energy can be efficaciously generated during reactions under a high temperature
65 condition; however, when the battery temperature exceeds a threshold value, the cathode crystal lattice of
66 the battery becomes unstable, thereby leading to a potential safety hazard. When the battery temperature
67 rises above 90°C, the solid electrolyte interface (SEI) film will experience exothermic decomposition and
68 thus battery performance will certainly decrease. On the contrary, under a low temperature condition, the
69 lithium ion activity noticeably decreases, leading to a decrease in polarization voltage and battery discharge
70 capacity. According to existing literature and operation requirements, the optimal charging/ discharging
71 temperature range for lithium-ion batteries is usually confined to within 0°C and 40°C to avoid rapid
72 degradation [37]. In a poorly designed thermal management system, heat accumulation can lead to
73 overheating, possibly producing a safety hazard and resulting in battery explosion in some extreme cases
74 [38]. Moreover, improperly charging a battery, or allowing the battery surface and internal temperatures to
75 go beyond the operating window, can possibly destroy its inner electro-chemical structure and thus reduce
76 charging efficiency and shorten the battery's lifespan [39].

77 To overcome these problems, a comprehensive charging strategy needs to be designed that fully
78 addresses the thermal effect, namely, by minimizing temperature increment during the charging process.
79 This is the main motivation of this study. In this paper, we focus on optimal and reliable battery charging
80 strategy design to minimize the temperature rise and shorten the charging time while considering the
81 parameters' variation at different temperatures. To summarize, the major contributions of this study can be

82 attributed to the following three aspects: First, we analyze the battery charging temperature variation
83 principle and establish the battery thermal model based on which two different cost functions are considered
84 in one objective function. One cost function is the charging energy loss, and the other one is the charging
85 temperature increment. Second, in terms of the thermal effect on battery charging performance, different
86 penalty factors are set in the objective function according to the low, high and optimal temperature,
87 respectively. Third, the objective function is solved with a closed-form expression, i.e., the Lagrange
88 multiplier method, which intuitively reveals the relationship among the optimal charging current, internal
89 resistance and polarization resistance.

90 Focusing on the charging optimization, this paper proposes a novel and applicable battery charging
91 strategy to optimize the charging temperature rise and energy loss. First, an equivalent circuit model (ECM),
92 a power loss model and a battery thermal model are established, and the genetic algorithm (GA) is
93 introduced to estimate the model parameters considering the thermal effect. Then, different penalty factors
94 are set in the objective function according to temperature constraints. The objective function is solved by a
95 closed-form expression, which intuitively reveals the relationship between the optimal charging current,
96 internal resistance and polarization resistance. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed optimal
97 charging strategy can shorten the charging time, lower the battery charging temperature rise and reduce
98 energy loss effectively.

99 The rest of the article is structured as follows. Section II demonstrates the battery test schedule,
100 modeling and its parameters identification at different temperatures. Section III formulates the optimal
101 charging objective function and constraints and solves the objective function with a closed-form expression,
102 followed by experimental validation in Section IV. Finally, the main conclusions are drawn in Section V.

103 II. BATTERY TESTING AND MODELING

104 A. Battery Test

105 A 26650-type cylindrical lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO_4) battery is tested in the experimental setup.
106 The nominal capacity and voltage of the test battery are 3.3 Ah and 3.2 V, respectively. During the test, the
107 voltage, current and temperature of the battery are monitored with a sampling frequency of 1 Hz. The test

108 flow chart is illustrated in Fig. 1 [40]. According to the battery specifications, the suitable operating
 109 temperature range that we tested is from 10°C to 50°C [4], and the interval is set to 10°C. Before conducting
 110 the experiment, the battery is placed in a thermal-controlled chamber to stabilize its internal/operating
 111 temperature. In each temperature stage, the experiment proceeds sequentially as follows: a CC discharge
 112 of 1C current, a 2-hour rest, a capacity test, a CC-CV charge test, a 2-hour rest, and a hybrid pulse power
 113 characterization (HPPC) test followed by a rest of 3 hours. Here C is the battery capacity value with unit
 114 Ampere-hour. The intention of the capacity test is to measure the battery discharge capacity under each
 115 temperature with different current rates. Here, the discharge rates are imposed to be 0.3C, 0.6C, 1C and
 116 1.5C, respectively. During the test, a thermocouple is attached to the battery surface to monitor the
 117 temperature variation. Fig. 2(a) exhibits the discharging profiles of the battery terminal voltage at 20°C. As
 118 can be clearly observed, the duration of the terminal voltage platform decreases as the discharge rate
 119 increases. Fig. 2(b) presents the voltage variation rate with the discharge capacity under a 1C discharge rate
 120 at different temperatures, and it can be found that the maximum discharge capacity increases with the
 121 operating temperature.

Fig. 1. Battery test schedule.

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123

Fig. 2. Voltage responses (a) With different discharge rates at 20°C. (b) With different temperatures at 1C.

The HPPC test is conducted to identify the model parameters, as shown in Fig. 3. Detailed information can be found in our previous publication [9]. During the experiment, the upper and lower voltage threshold and the current cutoff value are set to 3.65 V, 2 V and 0.05 C, respectively.

Fig. 3. HPPC test profiles at 20 °C.

B. Battery Modeling

In this paper, minimization of both the battery charging power loss and charging temperature increase is considered as one optimization target. Given this objective, the battery ECM, battery thermal model and power loss model are built simultaneously and analyzed in depth.

138 1). Battery Equivalent Circuit Model

139 In this study, a one-order resistance-capacitance (RC) ECM is built considering computational
 140 complexity and model precision, as shown in Fig. 4 [41].

141
 142 Fig. 4. One-order RC ECM.
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144 The one-order RC ECM includes an RC network, an OCV source and a resistor connected in series
 145 topology. According to the battery ECM, we can formulate the following equations to simulate voltage
 146 responses across the OCV source, the voltage drop on V_p , and R_0 . Note that I is negative for discharging
 147 and positive for charging in this paper.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dV_p}{dt} = \frac{I}{C_p} - \frac{V_p}{R_p \cdot C_p} \\ V_t = R_0 I + V_p + V_{OCV} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

149 The discrete SOC calculation can be expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} s(t) &= s(t-1) + (I(t-1)T_s)/C_b \\ &= s(0) + \left(T_s \sum_{j=0}^{t-1} I(j) \right) / C_b \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

151 where $s(0)$ is defined as the initial SOC value, C_b represents the battery nominal capacity, and T_s is
 152 the sampling interval time, i.e., 1 s in this study.

153 Based on (1) and (2), the discrete equation of this system can be presented as,

$$\begin{cases}
V_p(k+1) = aV_p(k) + bI(k) \\
V_l(k+1) = R_0 I(k+1) + V_p(k+1) + V_{ocv}(k+1) \\
s(k+1) = s(k) + T_s / C_b I(k)
\end{cases} \quad (3)$$

155 where $a = \exp(-T_s/\tau)$, $b = R_p \cdot (1-a)$, and τ is the time constant, which can be calculated by $R_p C_p$.

156 2). Battery Power Loss Model

157 Based on the established ECM shown in Fig. 4, the charging power loss model can be calculated.
158 Power loss during the charging process is divided into two parts, i.e., the internal resistance loss and the
159 polarization resistance loss, which can be calculated as,

$$\begin{cases}
P_{R_0} = I^2 R_0 \\
P_{R_p} = V_p^2 / R_p
\end{cases} \quad (4)$$

161 Hence, the instantaneous power loss can be expressed as,

$$P_{loss} = P_{R_0} + P_p = I^2 R_0 + V_p^2 / R_p \quad (5)$$

163 3). Battery Thermal Model

164 The thermal energy of a battery is mainly comprised of four sources, i.e., reversible heat, polarization
165 heat, Joule thermal and transferred heat [18, 42, 43]. For simplification, we assume that the battery's surface
166 temperature is uniformly distributed, thus the battery can be considered as a particle. Consequently, the
167 battery thermal model behavior can be expressed as,

$$C_h \frac{dT}{dt} = Q_r + Q_p + Q_j - Q_i \quad (6)$$

169 where C_h represents the battery thermal capacity, T expresses the battery temperature, and Q_p and
170 Q_j denote the polarized thermal power and the Joule thermal power, as shown in (4). Q_r and Q_i are the
171 reversible thermal power induced by entropy change and the thermal power transferred to the surroundings,
172 respectively, which can be calculated as,

$$\begin{cases}
Q_r = T \Delta S \frac{I}{eF} \\
Q_i = hA(T - T_{ope})
\end{cases} \quad (7)$$

174 where ΔS represents the entropy change, as expressed in (8), e describes the charging number of
 175 electrons per reaction, F is the Faraday constant, A means the battery surface area, T_{ope} expresses the
 176 operating temperature controlled by the thermal chamber, and h represents the heat transfer coefficient.
 177 Thus, we attain:

$$178 \quad \Delta S = eF \frac{\partial E}{\partial T} \quad (8)$$

179 In which E is the open circuit potential. By discretizing (4) and (6)-(8), we can attain,

$$180 \quad T(t+1) = T(t) + \frac{I^2 R_0 + \frac{V_p^2}{R_p} + T(t)I \frac{\partial E}{\partial T} - Ah(T(t) - T_{ope})}{mC_h} \quad (9)$$

181 where m is the weight of the battery. Here, we assume that $T(0) = T_{ope}$.

182 *C. Parameter Identification*

183 In this study, the temperature effect is taken into account when identifying the battery model
 184 parameters. Fig. 5 shows the capacity test results with different discharge rates and temperatures. As can
 185 be seen, the influence of the discharge rate on battery capacity is observable when the operating temperature
 186 is below 30°C. In contrast, when the operating temperature is above 30°C, the discharge rate shows
 187 negligible influence on the capacity. The battery capacity ratio is shown in Fig. 6 at different temperatures
 188 with a discharge current of 1C, and the battery capacity clearly decreases with a drop in temperature. Only
 189 95.3% of the available capacity is released when the temperature drops to 10°C; however, when the
 190 temperature is higher than 30°C, the capacity increase is not obvious. In order to model this relationship, a
 191 piecewise linearization is employed,

$$192 \quad \gamma = \frac{C_T}{C_b} \quad (10)$$

193 where C_T denotes the battery capacity at different temperatures.

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Fig. 5. Capacity comparison with different discharge rates and temperatures.

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Fig. 6. Battery capacity at different temperatures.

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After data processing and identification, the OCV with respect to different SOC is shown in Fig. 7.

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When the SOC is located within 30% to 90%, the OCV is relatively stable, i.e., between 3.28 V and 3.34

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V. Note that for normal operation of EVs, the battery SOC is only operated in a restricted range, i.e., 20%

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or 30% to 100%; as such, we set the battery SOC range from 20% to 90% for general consideration in this

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study [44]. It can be found from Fig. 7 that when the SOC changes from 20% to 90%, the OCV exhibits

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little difference at different temperatures.

Fig. 7. Battery OCV versus SOC at different temperatures.

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208 The other parameters, i.e., internal resistance, polarization resistance and the time constant, are
 209 identified based on the GA. More details about the identification algorithm can be referred to in our earlier
 210 works [9, 45, 46].

211 Here, the root mean square error (RMSE) is employed to evaluate the identification efficacy between
 212 the output of the established ECM and the HPPC experiment data,

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (V_{model} - V_{test})^2} \quad (11)$$

214 where N denotes the number of test sampling points, V_{model} denotes the terminal voltage of the
 215 established model, and V_{test} is the data from the HPPC test.

216 Based on the identification results, we find that R_0 remains almost unchanged with different battery
 217 SOC levels but decreases as the temperature rises. The detailed variation with respect to temperature is
 218 listed in Table I. Other parameters, including polarization resistance R_p and time constant τ , are
 219 determined with different operating temperatures and battery SOC levels. The correlations among SOC,
 220 R_p , τ and temperature are given in Table II and Table III.

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Table I. R_0 at different operating temperatures.

Temperature (°C)	10	20	30	40	50
R_0 (mΩ)	26.9	22.1	17.9	17.3	15.7

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Table II. R_p at different operating temperatures and SOC.

SOC	10°C (mΩ)	20°C (mΩ)	30°C (mΩ)	40°C (mΩ)	50°C (mΩ)
0.900	5.2	9.4	5.2	1.2	3.9
0.795	7.3	11.0	7.1	3.4	4.5
0.691	6.8	10.5	8.3	2.5	5.1
0.588	7.1	10.0	8.8	4.4	5.1
0.484	7.9	10.0	10.2	4.7	5.2
0.380	8.8	11.2	10.7	4.8	5.7
0.275	9.6	11.3	12.1	6.3	6.0
0.171	10.2	16.0	15.0	6.8	8.3

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Table III. τ at different operating temperatures and SOC.

SOC	10°C	20°C	30°C	40°C	50°C
0.900	10.6977	21.0424	8.1348	2.6439	9.6444
0.795	12.4498	23.3691	13.1733	6.2818	17.8490
0.691	13.0672	22.4241	19.5291	8.0746	19.0938
0.588	12.8695	21.7514	17.0462	9.5488	17.4880
0.484	13.4618	23.7675	19.5753	8.6595	16.5837
0.380	15.1991	24.8135	23.2931	12.4775	16.1722
0.275	16.5951	23.0962	35.6878	12.9229	17.4394
0.171	23.6289	36.0655	48.2621	15.2458	22.8531

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As discussed above, when the operating temperature is 30°C, the battery can release more energy, the plateau area occupies a larger range and simultaneously, internal resistance and polarization resistance are lower. Thus, in this study, we assume that 30°C is regarded as the optimal operating temperature.

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After identifying the parameters, $R_0 = f_{R_0}(T)$, $R_p = f_{R_p}(T, s)$, $\tau = f_{\tau}(T, s)$ and $V_{ocv} = f_{ocv}(s)$ can be built based on linear interpolation, as shown in Tables I through III and Fig. 7, respectively.

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D. Model Validation

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A comparison of the real experimental voltage and the ECM output is demonstrated in Fig. 8. The largest error spikes appear when the load current jumps abruptly. It can be seen that the maximum absolute error (ME) is less than 0.08 V. In addition, the mean absolute error (MAE), mean square error (MSE) and R^2 are introduced to evaluate the overall performance of the model and parameters, as formulated in (12). The model validation performance can be found in Table IV. From this point, we can conclude that the model can capture battery dynamics properly.

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$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} ME = \max(|V_{model} - V_{test}|) \\ MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (V_{test,i} - V_{model,i})^2 \\ MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |V_{test,i} - V_{model,i}| \\ R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (V_{test,i} - V_{model,i})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N \left(V_{test,i} - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N V_{test,i} \right)^2} \end{array} \right. \quad (12)$$

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241

Fig. 8. Equivalent circuit model validation results.

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Table IV. Summary of the model estimation performance.

ME (V)	MSE	RMSE (V)	MAE	R^2
0.08	0.00008	0.008	0.0017	0.9977

243

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Table V summarizes the thermal model validation results at different initial SOC values. According to the discussion mentioned above, the battery power loss model can be included in the thermal model. As can be seen in Table V, the maximum error is 0.67°C , which occurs at a low initial charging SOC with a high current, confirming that the built thermal model and charging power loss model can simulate the battery temperature and power loss characterizations with high accuracy.

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Table V. Thermal model validation results.

$s(0)$	Charging rate	Simulation result ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Experimental result ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Absolute error ($^\circ\text{C}$)
20%	1.5C	3.78	4.31	-0.67
	1C	1.89	1.86	0.03
	0.8C	1.38	1.35	0.03
	0.5C	0.71	0.80	-0.09
	0.3C	0.35	0.39	-0.04
40%	1.5C	2.64	3.05	-0.41

1C	1.64	1.99	-0.35
0.8C	1.08	1.28	-0.20
0.5C	0.56	0.74	-0.18
0.3C	0.29	0.33	-0.04

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III. OPTIMAL CHARGING FORMULATION

A. Objective Function Formulation

252 As described in Section I, two important factors are used to evaluate battery charging performance,
 253 namely the charging loss and charging temperature increase. According to the battery power loss model,
 254 the cost function that quantifies the energy loss can be formulated as,
 255

$$256 \quad J_{loss} = \sum_{k=1}^n \left(I^2(k)R_0 + \frac{V_p^2(k)}{R_p} \right) T_s \quad (13)$$

257 where J_{loss} is the cost function of the charging energy loss and n is the charging step. According to (3),
 258 $V_p(k)$ can be reformulated as,

$$259 \quad V_p(k) = \alpha^k V_p(0) + b \sum_{l=0}^{k-1} \alpha^{k-1-l} I(l) \quad (14)$$

260 Assuming $V_p(0) = 0$, we can attain

$$261 \quad J_{loss} = \sum_{k=1}^n \left(I(k)^2 R_0 + \frac{b^2 \sum_{l=0}^{k-1} \alpha^{2k-2-2l} I(l)^2}{R_p} \right) T_s \quad (15)$$

262 and its simplified expression can be rewritten as,

$$263 \quad J_{loss} = T_s \sum_{k=1}^n (\alpha(k) I(k)^2) \quad (16)$$

264 where $\alpha(k) = R_0 + \beta(k)$ and $\beta(k) = \frac{b^2}{R_p} \sum_{l=0}^{n-k} a^{2l} = \frac{b^2}{R_p} \frac{1 - a^{2n-2k+2}}{1 - a^2}$.

265 By incorporating the battery thermal model and defining the temperature increment as $\tilde{T}(t) = T(t) - T_{ope}$,
 266 we can calculate $\tilde{T}(k+1)$ based on $\tilde{T}(t)$ and (5) being substituted into (9),

$$267 \quad \tilde{T}(k+1) = (1-c)\tilde{T}(k) + dP_{loss}(k) \quad (17)$$

268 where $c = Ah / (mC_h)$, $d = 1/(mC_h) = c/(Ah)$, and $\tilde{T}(0) = 0$. Similar to $V_p(k)$, $\tilde{T}(k)$ can be reformulated
 269 as,

$$270 \quad \tilde{T}(k) = d \sum_{l=1}^{k-1} (1-c)^{k-l-1} P_{loss}(l) \quad (18)$$

271 Now, the cost function for the temperature rise, i.e., J_{temp} , can be formulated as,

$$272 \quad J_{temp} = \tilde{T}(n) = d \sum_{l=1}^{n-1} (1-c)^{n-l-1} P_{loss}(l) \quad (19)$$

273 Consequently, the final objective function J_{charge} can be formulated as,

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_{charge} &= \theta_1 J_{loss} + \theta_2 J_{temp} \\
 &= T_s \theta_1 \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (\alpha(k) I(k)^2) + \theta_2 d \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (1-c)^{n-k-1} P_{loss}(k) \\
 274 \quad &= T_s \theta_1 \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (\alpha(k) I(k)^2) + \theta_2 d \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (1-c)^{n-k-1} \alpha(k) I(k)^2_s \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} I(k)^2 \left(\theta_1 T_s \alpha(k) + \theta_2 d (1-c)^{n-k-1} \alpha(k) \right) \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} I(k)^2 \sigma(k)
 \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

275 where $\sigma(k) = \theta_1 T_s \alpha(k) + \theta_2 d (1-c)^{n-k-1} \alpha(k)$. Here, two penalty factors, θ_1 and θ_2 , are added to the objective
 276 function. When the operating temperature is lower than the optimal operating temperature, i.e., 30°C, the
 277 objective function changes to minimize the charging energy loss while the battery is heated by its internal
 278 resistance. Under this condition, θ_1 and θ_2 are set as 1 and 0, respectively. When the operating
 279 temperature is higher than the optimal operating temperature, normally, the temperature increment is
 280 limited within 1°C to 5°C and the energy loss is more than 0.65 Wh. In this case, however, both factors can
 281 be regarded as having the same influence, and thus θ_1 and θ_2 are both set to 1. As such, we can determine
 282 that

$$283 \quad \begin{cases} \theta_1 = 1 \\ \theta_2 = \begin{cases} 0, & T_{ope} < 30 \\ 1, & T_{ope} \geq 30 \end{cases} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

284 In addition, it is worth pointing out that the objective function can include other functions related to battery
 285 charging current or efficiency optimization; therefore, the optimization framework that we have proposed
 286 is still feasible.

287 To guarantee charging safety and rationality, some constraints are imposed in the optimal process. It
 288 is assumed that the optimal charging process takes n seconds to attain a specified target SOC, i.e., s_n , and
 289 the initial SOC $s(0)$ is set to s_0 . In addition, s_0 and s_n should be limited to between 0 and 1. Thus,

$$290 \quad 0 \leq s(0) = s_0 \leq s(n) = s_n \leq 1 \quad (22)$$

291 According to (2), this relationship can be rewritten as,

$$292 \quad s_n - s_0 - T_s / C_b \cdot \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} I(k) = 0 \quad (23)$$

293 Note that when a battery is charged based on the optimal current, the terminal voltage should be lower than
 294 or at most equal to the maximum safe charging voltage threshold. Moreover, the charging current should
 295 not exceed the maximum allowed charging current specified by the battery manufacturer,

$$296 \quad I_k \leq I_{\max} \quad (24)$$

297 *B. Objective Function Optimization*

298 In order to determine the optimal charging strategy, the Lagrange multiplier method is introduced in
 299 this study for achieving the extreme value of the objective function. We assume that both (20) and (23)
 300 have continuous first partial derivatives, such that the Lagrange function can be defined with a new variable
 301 λ , the Lagrange multiplier

$$302 \quad L = J_{\text{charge}} + \lambda \left(s_n - s_0 - T_s / C_b \cdot \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} I(k) \right) \quad (25)$$

303 The derivatives of Lagrange function L with respect to $I(k)$ and λ are

$$304 \quad \begin{cases} \frac{\partial L}{\partial I} = 2\sigma(k)I(k) - \lambda \frac{T_s}{C_b} \\ \frac{\partial L}{\partial \lambda} = s_n - s_0 - \frac{T_s}{C_b} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} I(k) \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

305 Two necessary conditions should be satisfied,

306
$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial L}{\partial I} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial L}{\partial \lambda} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

307 Given this, $I(k)$ and λ can be determined as,

308
$$\begin{cases} I(k) = \frac{\lambda T_s}{2\sigma(k)C_b} \\ \lambda = \frac{2(s_n - s_0)C_b^2 \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sigma(k)}{T_s^2} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

309 By solving (28), the optimal current is yielded as,

310
$$I(k) = \frac{(s_n - s_0)C_b \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \sigma(k)}{T_s \sigma(k)} \quad (29)$$

311 Based on (29), the optimal charging current profile is related to n and $\sigma(k)$, where $\sigma(k)$ is a function
 312 of R_0 and R_p . n and the optimal charging current are computed via the following steps, as shown in

313 **Error! Reference source not found..**

314 1) Initialize n ;

315 2) Solve (29) with the constraint conditions listed in (22)-(24);

316 3) Calculate s_n ;

317 4) If $|s_n - 0.9| \leq \xi$, where ξ is set as 0.0001, then the optimal n is the previous value and the optimal

318 charging current is the current solution; otherwise, update n and go to step 2) until the convergence

319 condition is met.

320

321 Fig. 9. The procedure for obtaining the optimal charging current.

322 In this manner, the optimal current profile can be resolved, by which the charger can charge the battery
 323 SOC from 20% to 90% while minimizing J_{charge} . In the next step, experimental verification is presented
 324 and the results are analyzed and discussed.

325 IV. VERIFICATION AND DISCUSSION

326 In this paper, experiments are designed and performed to validate the feasibility and generality of the
 327 proposed optimal charging strategy. First, three different charging current profiles are applied as the
 328 benchmark to manifest the feasibility of the proposed charging method. Second, different operating
 329 temperatures are applied to test the robustness of the strategy. Third, the proposed optimal charging strategy
 330 is implemented using another type of battery with lithium nickel-manganese-cobalt oxide (LiNMC) as its
 331 anode materials to demonstrate the algorithm's generality. Fourth, three different aged cells are
 332 experimented on based on the optimal charging current to extend the strategy's flexibility.

333 A. Charging Strategy Verification

334 Practically, the CC charging method is the simplest charging strategy, which is regarded as the standard
 335 charging strategy to compare with the proposed optimal charging strategy. Here, to prove the feasibility of

336 the proposed charging strategy, six different CC profiles, including the optimal charging profiles, are
 337 compared at an operating temperature of 30°C. These charging current profiles are applied to charge the
 338 battery until the SOC reaches s_n . The proposed charging method is applied to optimize the CC strategy,
 339 including a 0.8C, 1C and 1.5C CC charging current.

340 The resolved charging current profiles and experimental results of the terminal voltage variation are
 341 illustrated in Fig. 10. It can be found from this profile that the charging current in the early stage changes
 342 slightly and begins to decrease after a period of charging. Long time reduction of the charging current at
 343 the end of the whole process results in a small drop in the terminal voltage, which is displayed in the 1C
 344 and 1.5C current curves. However, for the 0.8C optimal charging current and terminal voltage curves, the
 345 charging current only reduces within a small range, and as such, the terminal voltage stops dropping. After
 346 charging the battery SOC from 20% to 90%, the battery keeps still for one hour, and the ending voltage for
 347 0.8C, 1C and 1.5C optimal charging is 3.3421 V, 3.3414 V and 3.3410V, respectively, which indicates that
 348 the maximum difference is less than 0.002 V. Therefore, the reduction in terminal voltage does not lead to
 349 a drop in the SOC, and we can conclude that the algorithm can reach the setting target precisely even with
 350 different planning trajectories. This can also prove the efficacy of the built battery ECM and thermal model
 351 from different perspectives.

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Fig. 10. Different charging profiles comparison: (a) Charging current curves; (b) Terminal voltage curves.

356 Fig. 11 presents the charging temperature rise under different charging strategies. The temperature
 357 increment based on the optimal charging strategy is lower than that of the normal CC charging strategy
 358 during the whole charging process. A comparison of these experimental results is illustrated in Table VI.
 359 Among these results, energy loss and charging time can be improved based on the proposed charging
 360 strategy. Fig. 12 shows the improvement of the proposed charging strategy over the traditional CC charging
 361 method. It can be found that the proposed strategy exhibits the capability of simultaneously optimizing the
 362 temperature increment, energy loss and charging time, going from 10.47% to 29.15%, 1.08% to 2.94% and
 363 0.7% to 1.01%, respectively, compared with the results of the CC charging strategy.

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Fig. 11. Different charging temperature increment profiles.

Table VI. Experimental results comparison given different charging strategies.

Charging strategy	Temperature increment (°C)	Energy loss (Wh)	Time (s)
0.8C CC	1.72	0.65	3152
0.8C Optimal charging	1.54	0.63	3130
1C CC	2.95	0.68	2521
1C Optimal charging	2.09	0.66	2503
1.5C CC	5.87	0.76	1681
1.5C Optimal charging	4.02	0.74	1664

Fig. 12. Improvements of the optimal strategy.

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To demonstrate the performance improvement when applying our proposed optimization strategy, the polarization voltage profiles based on the CC strategy with 1C current and the corresponding optimal charging strategy are shown in Fig. 13. Between 0 s and 1630 s, the polarization voltage based on the optimal charging strategy is inferior to that based on the CC charging strategy; on the other hand, after 1630 s, the polarization voltage of the optimal charging strategy is higher than that based on the CC charging method. However, at the end of the charging process, a smaller current is implemented by the optimal strategy to decrease battery polarization. Hence, we can say that the polarization voltage of the improved charging strategy is lower than that of CC charging, and as a result, the charging time, temperature increment and energy loss of the optimal charging method are lower than that of the CC charging method.

Fig. 13. Polarization voltage variation under various charging methods.

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383 *B. Verification Study under Different Operating Temperatures*

384 In order to validate the robustness of the proposed strategy, a battery is charged with the optimal
 385 charging current profiles, plotted in Fig. 14, at different operating temperatures. The experimental results
 386 are listed in Table VII. Fig. 15 shows the improvements in terms of temperature increase, energy loss and
 387 charging time, which reveal that the proposed strategy performs superiorly in reducing temperature
 388 increment, energy loss and charging time in comparison with the CC charging strategy. This performance
 389 is primarily attributed to the lower polarization voltage brought about by the optimal charging current. It
 390 can be inferred that no matter whether the environmental temperature is within its normal range, the built
 391 charging algorithm is still capable of achieving satisfactory charging performance. In addition, it is worth
 392 pointing out that the built charging strategy elevates the battery temperature to some extent, and the energy
 393 loss can be decreased even when the environmental temperature is less than the optimal temperature.

394

395 Fig. 14. Charging current profiles under various operating temperatures.

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Table VII. Experimental results comparison under various operating temperatures.

Operating temperature (°C)	Charging strategy	Temperature increment (°C)	Energy loss (Wh)	Charging time (s)
20	CC	5.57	1.00	1681
	Optimal	7.06	0.77	1601
30	CC	5.87	0.76	1681
	Optimal	4.02	0.74	1664
40	CC	4.93	0.67	1681
	Optimal	2.93	0.65	1574
50	CC	5.02	0.62	1701
	Optimal	3.85	0.61	1607

Fig. 15. Improvements of the proposed charging algorithm under various operating temperatures.

C. Verification with Different Battery Types

To extend the applicability of the proposed strategy, a different battery with LiNMC as its anode, of which the nominal capacity is 5 Ah and the rated voltage is 3.6 V, is experimented on. All experiments are carried out at 30°C, and the 1C CC charging method is benchmarked to compare the charging performance. Fig. 16 shows the battery temperature varies with SOC during the charging process. It is evident that the temperature increases more slowly based on the built strategy than based on the CC charging strategy.

Fig. 16. Battery temperature with various SOC values.

The experimental results for different charging strategies are compared in Fig. 17 and Table VIII. Table VIII indicates that the charging temperature increment, charging energy loss and charging time of the LiNMC battery, based on our method, are reduced by 19.43%, 16.22% and 1.19%, respectively. To sum

412 up, we can conclude that the proposed methodology can be effectively extended to other types of lithium-
 413 ion batteries only if the internal resistance varies with the battery SOC.

414

415 Fig. 17. Comparison of experimental results for various charging strategies.

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Table VIII Experimental results comparison with different battery types.

Operating temperature (°C)	Battery type	Charging strategy	Temperature increment (°C)	Energy loss (Wh)	Charging time (s)	Ending SOC
30	LiNMC/C	CC	5.61	1.85	2521	0.900
		Optimal	4.52	1.55	2491	0.899
		Improvement	19.43%	16.22%	1.19%	/

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D. Verification Study with Aging Cells

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In addition, the flexibility of the strategy is validated with batteries of different aging states in this study. To accelerate battery degradation, the cell is cycled with a charging current of 0.5C and a discharging current of 2C at 25°C. After a certain cycle operation, the battery is experimented on to calibrate its SOH first. In order to make the environmental conditions consistent, all the tests are carried out at 30°C, and the 0.5C CC charging method is benchmarked to compare the charging performance. The charging performance versus the SOH values are presented in Fig. 18 and Table IX. It can be noticed that the charging temperature rise, energy loss and charging time of the built strategy are reduced by 7.81%, 10.14% and 9.68%, respectively, compared with those of the CC charging strategy, until the SOH reaches 82.38%. This proves that even as the battery degrades, the proposed algorithm is still effective in reaching the setting target.

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Fig. 18. Charging performance vs. SOH values at 30°C.

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Table IX Experimental results comparison with different aged cells.

Operating temperature (°C)	SOH (%)	Charging strategy	Temperature increment (°C)	Energy loss (Wh)	Charging time (s)
30	95.34	CC	2.13	0.77	2403
		Optimal	1.91	0.70	2166
		Improvement	10.33%	9.09%	9.86%
	83.41	CC	2.40	0.76	2102
		Optimal	2.16	0.67	1898
		Improvement	10.00%	11.84%	9.71%
	82.38	CC	2.56	0.69	2076
		Optimal	2.36	0.62	1875
		Improvement	7.81%	10.14%	9.68%

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V. CONCLUSIONS

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To reduce both the temperature increment and energy loss of battery charging, an optimal battery charging strategy is proposed. An ECM that considers the effect of the operating temperature, a battery power loss model and a battery thermal model are established with detailed mathematical analysis. The optimal charging current profile is derived based on the cost function, which is a weighted sum of the energy loss and temperature increment index. By comparing the proposed charging strategy with the traditional strategy through experimental validation, the proposed strategy is shown to possess strong advantages in the following four aspects:

440

(i) The new method accurately reveals the relationship between optimal charging current, internal resistance and polarization resistance.

441

442 (ii) The new method is capable of reducing the temperature increment, energy loss and charging time
443 by more than 10.47%, 1.08% and 0.7%, respectively, when compared with the CC charging strategy.

444 (iii) The temperature effect on the battery parameters is considered in the proposed strategy and thus
445 a wide application temperature window can be guaranteed.

446 (iv) The proposed strategy can be expanded to different battery types and different aging status.

447 The next step of our work will focus on the SOH and the battery lifetime influence induced by the
448 proposed charging method. Furthermore, a battery pack optimal charging method may also be a potential
449 research focus.

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458

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